

**DESIGN OF DETECTION OF LIVESTOCK DISEASES BASED ON DATA
OBTAINED THROUGH RFID TECHNOLOGY**

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Abstract: This article examines the process of designing a program for detecting cattle diseases based on information obtained through RFID technology, which serves to develop such a system. This article also presents the analysis of veterinary data obtained through RFID technology and the analysis of experimental data on veterinary diseases.

Keywords: RFID technology, disease detection, design process, UML diagram, veterinary data analysis, ER diagram.

Introduction

Today, one of the most important sectors of the economy is the livestock sector. In this sector, increasing efficiency and improving the quality of livestock products, as well as ensuring the health of livestock, is of great importance. Research and technological developments conducted in the world are mainly aimed at developing innovative methods for early detection and treatment of diseases, using sensor and IoT technologies to monitor many physiological indicators of livestock in real time, and using machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms to analyze this indicator data.

As a result, specialized software for smart livestock farms is being developed based on scientific research into automatic disease detection. For example, systems

such as *CowManager*, *Afimilk*, and *DairyComp* help farmers improve livestock health and production efficiency.

RFID mainly consists of three parts: a data reader (reader, interrogator); an identifier (tag, label, marking, transponder, card, key fob) and a computer system. The working principle of RFID technology is as follows: the RFID tag is pre-loaded with data representing a unique code; the RFID reader is a special device that reads the tag data; the RFID antennas form an electromagnetic field that provides wireless communication between the reader and the tag. In short, the reader sends a request, and the tag responds[1].

Important issues include the development of all branches of veterinary medicine and animal husbandry, including cattle breeding, coordination of selection work, and the development and implementation of targeted state programs in these areas.

The solution to this problem is to introduce effective forms of knowledge and information dissemination integrated with the introduction of information and communication technologies in district (city) departments and subordinate organizations of the department, the expansion of research, education and advisory services in animal husbandry and its branches[2].

Materials and methods The study is based on the analysis of veterinary data obtained through RFID technology and the analysis of experimental data on veterinary diseases. The use of ER diagrams in building a database for identifying cattle diseases is effective. The structure of the procedure for developing and using a veterinary software package is presented in Figure 1.

in the user table. Most of the created tables (general_examination, general_blood_examination, animal, vetpoint) are related to the veterinary service.

To develop a software system, it is essential to design it. Therefore, an ER diagram (Entity Relationship diagram) visually reflects the data structure in the program. Based on this diagram, a data management system is created, which helps to predetermine and expand the capabilities of the program.

To develop a software system, it is essential to design it. Therefore, an ER diagram visually reflects the data structure in the program through Entity Relationship diagram. Based on this diagram, a data management system is created, which helps to predetermine and expand the capabilities of the program. An ER diagram helps to optimize data management processes in the program by identifying relationships between various objects. A database is created based on this diagram and provides the following capabilities[3].

Result

The image shows a login form with the following elements:

- Title: **Tizimga kirish**
- Label: **Telefon raqam**
- Input field: +998 XX XXX XX XX
- Label: **Parol**
- Input field: Parol
- Button: **Kirish** (green)

Figure 2. Access to the control panel

Figure 3. The main window of the control panel

Figure 4. Information from RFID

Experiments: This model is used to store cattle practices (experiments). Each experiment contains information related to the name, number of parts, status (active or inactive), user, and creation time.

Here you can make changes to all sections and add users. For now, these tasks can only be performed by the administrator.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in order for the program to provide convenient and reliable data, many tables are created to supplement the above main table data. And these tables are related to each other from the point of view of presenting data. In the same way, the tables are connected to each other in such a way that a summary report is formed that allows for a general analysis by supplementing the data. This contributes greatly to the development of software.

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